

Aryl Derivatives from Castor Oil. Part II.¹ Phenylated Methyl Ricinoleate

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The reaction product of methyl ricinoleate with benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride was studied by chromatographic methods (TLC, column and GLC). The identification of the different components in the reaction mixture was accomplished by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Evidence for the presence of diphenyl saturated esters, in addition to monophenyl unsaturated esters was obtained. From the mass spectra, the location of branching in the fatty acid chain was studied. Phenylation gave position isomers with substitutions at carbon 5 to carbon 17 in the fatty acid chain.

RICINOLEIC acid was reported by Dey *et al.*² to be phenylated at the hydroxyl group leaving the double bond intact when using sulphuric acid as condensing agent. In the present work Friedel-Crafts condensation using anhydrous aluminium chloride with methyl ricinoleate and benzene was studied. The dropwise addition of methyl ricinoleate to the suspension of anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene represents the best condition for the reaction. Within less than 30 min the reaction was practically complete as revealed by the drop in iodine value and the disappearance of the hydroxyl group as well as the rise in the saponification equivalent (Iod. val. 15.8; OH% nil; sap. equiv. 370) as compared with 84.8; 5.4; 313.4 respectively, for the original ricinoleate.

Although mass spectral information about methyl esters of saturated fatty acids³ is extensive, only a few workers reported specific analysis of unsaturated⁴ and phenylated⁵ esters. Smith *et al.*⁶ reported that methyl phenylstearate shows fragmentation taking

place at the bond between C and R₁ [cf. (a) in scheme 1] or R₂ [cf. (b)] like that proposed by Grubb and Meyerson⁷ for alkyl benzenes.

The GC/MS of the methyl ricinoleate condensation product revealed a peak for methyl stearate representing 14.4%, another peak for methyl oleate (8.2%), two peaks for methyl phenyloctadecanoate (12.4%), three peaks for methyl phenyloctadecenoate (47.9%), two peaks for methyl diphenylstearate (14.6%) and two unidentified peaks (2.5%).

From the mass spectrum the location of branching in the fatty acid chain could be studied. The phenylated products were found to be a mixture of all position isomers with substitution at carbon 5 to carbon 17 in the fatty acid chain.

Experimental

Starting material. Methyl ricinoleate was prepared from castor oil⁸, methyl 12-hydroxystearate from hydrogenated castor oil⁹, and methyl oleate⁹ from oleic acid (M & B) 99% pure. The products were fractionally distilled in vacuo (cf. Table 1).

Phenylated methyl esters. Several experiments were carried out using benzene as the reactant⁶ to find out the proper condition to obtain the best yield of the phenylated product through variation in the ratio of catalyst to reactant, the temperature of the reaction, the duration of heating and the order of addition. The rate of phenylation was also studied (cf. Table 2).

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Phenylated methyl ricinoleate was introduced in the mass spectrometer through a gas chromatograph. With GC/MS system MAT III, the built in GC of the type Varian Aerograph 1400-II Special, the gas chromatographic detector is accommodated in the source housing of the mass spectrometer. The sample enters the

TABLE 1—METHYL ESTERS OF FATTY ACIDS

Esters	B.p. °C/mm Hg	n_D^{25}	Iod. val.	Sap. equiv.	OH%
Methyl ricinoleate	186–194/1.5	1.4609	84.8	313.4	5.4
Methyl 12-hydroxystearate	202–204/4.0	—	3.0	—	4.2
Methyl oleate	156–159/1.5	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2—PHENYLATION OF METHYL ESTERS

Mol. ratio ester : AlCl ₃ : benzene	Order of addition	Time of addition (min.)	Reaction time (min.)	Iod. val.	Sap. equiv.	OH%
<i>Methyl ricinoleate</i>						
1 : 1.1 : 1 in tetrachloroethane	ester (a) to AlCl ₃ (b)	30	0	84.8	313.4	5.4
			30	30.1	—	0.4
			60	31.1	—	0.6
			120	32.4	—	0.5
1 : 1.1 : excess	(a) to (b)	30	30	30.8	328.0	nil
			60	27.8	320.0	nil
			120	25.1	338.0	nil
1 : 2.2 : excess	(a) to (b)	30	30	18.2	358.2	nil
			60	16.1	354.1	nil
			120	18.9	358.5	nil
			180	15.6	357.8	nil
1 : 2.2 : excess	(a) to (b)	15	60	24.4	368.6	nil
			5	60	15.8	370.0
	(b) to (a)	5	30	15.1	370.0	nil
			30	20.0	350.0	nil
			30	18.1	351.0	nil
1 : 2.2 : excess (the reaction carried out at 80°)	(a) to (b)	30	60	18.1	345.0	nil
			120	19.2	344.0	nil
			180	18.1	349.0	nil
			30	134.8	—	nil
1 : 1.1 : 0.0 in tetrachloroethane	(a) to (b)	30	60	141.3	—	nil
			120	127.9	—	nil
			180	118.6	—	nil
			<i>Methyl oleate</i>			
1 : 1.1 : excess	(a) to (b)	30	0	85.6	—	—
			30	9.7	353.0	—
			60	8.6	350.0	—
			120	7.4	346.2	—
			180	6.7	348.5	—
<i>Methyl 12-hydroxystearate</i>						
1 : 1.1 : excess	(b) to (a)	30	0	3.0	292.3	4.2
			30	8.9	340.7	0.9
			60	8.6	337.3	0.8
			120	7.4	341.6	0.3
			240	5.2	351.9	nil

electron impact ionization detector (EID) and the ion source of the mass spectrometric detector (MSD) at the same time. The column was 5.1/8' steel (5% SE 30) heated at 220°–250°, and the flow rate was 100–110 ml/min. In the (MSD) source the ions are generated in the conventional way by impact with 80 eV electron. The operating temperature of the source is 200°. The percent composition of the different components were calculated by the internal normalization method (cf. Table 3).

Discussion

In the Friedel-Crafts reaction of methyl ricinoleate with excess of benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, the addition of benzene to the 9,10-double bond appeared to proceed through proton addition from H⁺AlCl₄⁻ to give an intermediate carbonium ion. Through hydride ion transfer a mixture of isomers with the phenyl group attached to different positions on the fatty acid chain is obtained.

TABLE 3—GC/MS OF PHENYLATED METHYL RICINOLEATE

Peak No.	Mol. Wt.	Component	% com- ponent
1	298	Methyl stearate	14.4
2	296	Methyl oleate	8.2
3	270	unidentified	1.2
4	287	unidentified	1.3
5	374	Methyl phenyloctadecanoate	1.3
6	374	" "	11.1
7	372	" phenyloctadecenoate	27.3
8	372	" "	47.9
9	372	" "	20.6
10	450	" diphenyloctadecanoate	10.6
11	450	" "	4.0

The formation of a diphenyl substituted fatty acid may proceed by any of the following mechanisms :

1) Coordination of aluminium chloride (Lewis acid) with the oxygen of the hydroxyl group in the monophenylated acid ester followed by the formation of a carbonium ion which may undergo any of the following reactions. (a) Direct phenylation to the diphenyl ester, or (b) the elimination of a proton from carbon atoms 11 or 13 to give an unsaturated phenyl ester which is further phenylated to the diphenyl ester.

2) Before phenylation of the double bond, the hydroxyl group is eliminated by removal of hydrogen from carbon 11 to give a conjugated diene (methyl octadeca-9, 10-11, 12-dienoate), or from carbon 13 to give (methyl octadeca-9, 10-12, 13-dienoate) which are then biphenylated to give the diphenyl ester.

However, the latter mechanism is excluded from the following facts :

- (i) no unphenylated diene ester was detected by gas chromatography,
- (ii) Schmidt¹⁰ found that arylat on of octadeca-9-enoic acid is a very fast process and takes place within less than five minutes, and
- (iii) methyl oleate was found to be more easily phenylated than methyl 12-hydroxystearate under the same conditions (cf. Table 2).

Attempts to separate or identify the components of the reaction mixture by TLC¹¹⁻¹⁴ or column chromatography¹⁵⁻¹⁷ were not successful. Attempted separation of the components of the mixture by PYE-Unicam research laboratory using preparative gas chromatograph series 105 was not successful. The latter method showed undefined peaks. GC/MS was resorted to as it is the most powerful method available for disclosing the structure of the branched fatty acids, (cf. Fig. 1).

GC/MS of the product

Mass spectrometry of the components of the first four peaks indicated that they are either degradation or unphenylated products. The mass spectrum of

peak 6 shows a molecular ion with m/e 374 which stands for methyl phenylstearate. The spectrum shows the m/e peaks reported in Tables 4 and 5.

Fig. 1. GC/MS of Phenylated Methyl Ricinoleate.

- 1) Methyl Stearate
- 2) Methyl Oleate
- 3 & 4) Unidentified
- 5 & 6) Methyl Phenylstearate
- 7, 8 & 9) Methyl Phenyloctadecenoate
- 10 & 11) Methyl Diphenylstearate.

These ions arise from the fragmentation at (a) or (b) (inter alia) to give ions (I) and (II), respectively. The base peak is at m/e 91 and appears to arise from fragmentation at (a) and (b) (Scheme 1) to give a radical ion $[C_6H_5CH]$ which picks up any hydrogen atom from another fragment and rearrange to give a propylium ion.

TABLE 4—PHENYL SUBSTITUTED ALKYL IONS (I)

$$[CH_3(CH_2)_x-CH-C_6H_5]^+$$

x	m/e	% abund.	x	m/e	% abund.	x	m/e	% abund.
0	103	27.4	5	175	5.0	9	231	2.7
1	119	16.3	6	189	5.1	10	245	1.8
2	133	10.5	7	203	1.4	11	259	0.8
3	147	7.3	8	217	2.8	12	273	0.6
4	161	5.4						

TABLE 5—PHENYL SUBSTITUTED ALKYL IONS CONTAINING A METHOXY CARBONYL GROUP

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} CH-(CH_2)_xCOOCH_3 \\ | \\ C_6H_5 \end{array} \right]^+$$

z	m/e	% abund.	z	m/e	% abund.	z	m/e	% abund.
3	191	0.8	5	219	1.9	7	247	1.0
4	205	1.3	6	233	1.5	8	261	0.9
						9	275	0.7

It is clear from the data in Table (4) that the % abundance decreases with increase in carbon chain. The absence of a peak corresponding to ion (I) with m/e larger than 273 can be taken as an evidence for the absence of any methyl phenylstearate in which the phenyl group is separated from the carbonyl ester group by less than 3 carbon atoms, i.e., the heaviest phenyl alkyl ion with m/e 273 will be

$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{12}-\text{CH} \\ | \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array} \right]^+$, which arises from fragmentation of methyl 5-phenylstearate. The ion

having m/e 105 $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3-\text{CH} \\ | \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array} \right]^+$ arises from fragmentation of methyl 17phenylstearate.

The absence of homologous peaks with m/e less than 191 is an evidence for the absence of phenyl isomers in which the phenyl group is attached to carbon atom nearer to the carbonyl ester group than carbon 3.

The ion m/e = (M-OCH₃)⁺ is the base peak in methyl acetate but its abundance is known to decrease with the increase in the length of the chain. The corresponding peak exists in the spectrum at m/e 343 with very low abundance (2.1%).

It can be concluded that the fragmentation pattern of fraction 6 discloses that it is composed of methyl phenylstearate isomers in which the phenyl group is attached to carbon 5 up to carbon 17.

The MS of peaks 7, 8 and 9 in the chromatogram correspond to monophenyl unsaturated esters. The molecular ion peaks in the spectra have m/e 372, which stands for methyl phenyloctadecenoate (M.W. 372). Double bond stabilises the parent peak ions

and this is reflected in the high intensity of the molecular ions of these components with % abundance 9.3, 6.3 and 3.0 for fractions 7, 8 and 9 respectively.

When the phenyl substitution and the double bond are conjugated no fragmentation, which destroys the conjugation, can result. Cleavage does occur on either side of the system and the ions resulting from cleavage alpha to the phenyl group are in greatest abundance. Also, in esters that have the substitution separated from the double bond by one methylene group, ions caused by α-cleavage to the phenyl group on the side closest to the olefinic group are much more abundant than those produced from cleavage on the other side of the phenyl group¹⁸.

Cleavage at both sides of the allylic structure produces ions $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH} \\ | \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array} \right]^+$ and $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ | \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array} \right]^+$

at m/e 116, with % abundance 4.4, 3.6, and 3.5 in the 7, 8 and 9 fractions, respectively. These radical ions pick up a hydrogen atom to give the base peak at 117.

This is a sound proof that unsaturation is conjugated with the phenyl group. Methyl phenyloctadecenoate could have any of the following structures (A) or (B) (cf. Scheme 2).

Isomers having structures (iii, iv) and (vii, viii) which contain a phenyl allylic group give rise to fragmentations with the same m/e values in the three fractions with different relative intensities. However, isomers having structure (vii) and (viii) which arise from the replacement of the hydroxyl group by the phenyl group while the original double bond is left intact or rearranged during the formation of the carbonium ion are not acceptable. From

Scheme 2

acid ester containing at least a $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}$ chain. This is also supported by the absence of fragment ions containing the ester group which have m/e values less than 281.

or its isomers which arises from fragmentation of methyl diphenylstearate in which one of the phenyl groups is attached preferentially to carbon 6 (cf. methyl 5,6-diphenylstearate)

Fragmentation at (b) gives peaks corresponding to phenyl substituted alkyl ions that have the m/e values shown in Table (9).

The absence of a peak with m/e larger than 259 can be taken as an indication that the product contains no methyl diphenylstearate in which one of the phenyl groups is separated from the carbonyl ester group by less than 4 carbon atoms, i.e., the heaviest ion with m/e 259 will be $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}-\text{CH} \\ | \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{array} \right]^+$

The failure to detect any fragment ion containing the ester group with m/e less than 191 excludes the presence of any diphenyl ester in which the second phenyl group is separated from the ester group by less than 3 carbon atoms.

Fragmentation at (c) produces phenyl substituted alkyl ions having the same m/e values as ions obtained from fragmentation at (b). It also gives rise to phenyl substituted ions containing the ester group, e.g. the isomer methyl 9,13-diphenylstearate when fragmented at (b) gives a fragment ion with m/e

TABLE 9—PHENYL SUBSTITUTED ALKYL IONS RESULTING FROM FRAGMENTATION AT (b)

		% abundance in						% abundance in			
$x+y$	m/e	fraction		$x+y$	m/e	fraction		$x+y$	m/e	fraction	
		10	11			10	11			10	11
0	105	11.5	29.4	4	161	2.9	9.1	8	217	1.2	1.8
1	119	7.0	15.2	5	175	2.0	5.8	9	231	1.2	2.4
2	133	3.7	9.1	6	189	2.2	3.0	10	245	1.0	6.1
3	147	3.7	12.1	7	203	1.4	3.3	11	259	1.0	2.1

TABLE 10—PHENYL SUBSTITUTED ALKYL IONS RESULTING FROM FRAGMENTATION AT (d)

		% abundance in						% abundance in			
$x+y$	m/e	fraction		$x+y$	m/e	fraction		$x+y$	m/e	fraction	
		10	11			10	11			10	11
0	195	5.4	6.4	4	251	2.4	6.1	8	307	1.4	2.1
1	209	2.9	7.0	5	265	1.9	3.9	9	321	0.9	1.5
2	223	3.4	7.3	6	279	1.0	2.7	10	335	0.7	—
3	237	3.6	10.6	7	293	1.7	2.9				

TABLE 11—ALKYL ION CONTAINING ESTER GROUP RESULTING FROM FRAGMENTATION AT (d)

		% abundance in						% abundance in			
z	m/e	fraction		z	m/e	fraction		z	m/e	fraction	
		10	11			10	11			10	11
1	73	1.9	5.2	6	143	13.4	17.3	11	213	1.9	3.3
2	87	3.2	5.1	7	157	8.1	7.3	12	227	3.4	3.6
3	101	1.2	3.0	8	171	2.7	6.4	13	241	3.1	3.9
4	115	8.0	11.8	9	185	2.2	5.8	14	255	3.7	4.7
5	129	13.4	17.6	10	199	1.7	3.3				

as that given by methyl 12,14-diphenylstearate when fragmented at (c).

Fragmentation at (d) produces phenyl substituted ions with peaks of m/e values 195, 209 ... etc. (cf. Table 10). These ions arise from diphenyl substituted fatty acid esters in which the phenyl groups are attached to carbon atom 5 to carbon atom 17, (x) varies from 0 to 11 and (y) from 11 to 0, while the sum of ($x+y$) does not exceed 11 and (z) is not less than 3.

The alkyl fragment ions containing a methoxy-carbonyl can have m/e values 73, 87, ... etc./cf. Table (11). The peak at m/e 255 is an evidence for the presence of a fragment ion in which $z = 14$. This ion arises from the fragmentation of methyl 16,17-diphenylstearate at the bond between carbon atoms 15 and 16. It can be concluded that (z) in the molecule can have values from 14 to 3.

It is evident from the above data concerning the fragmentation at (a), (b), (c) and (d) that the ions detected in the mass spectra of fractions 10 and 11 arise from methyl diphenyloctadecanoate isomers in which the phenyl groups are attached to carbon atom 5 up to carbon atom 17, (x) varies from 0 to 11 and (y) from 11 to 0, while the sum of ($x+y$) does not exceed 11 and (z) is not less than 3. The calculated total number of isomers is 78.

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